

GIGO: Automated Recovery of Price Time Series from Chart Images via Anchor-Point Calibration

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Abstract

Online price-tracking platforms such as CamelCamelCamel render historical price data exclusively as rasterised chart images, without exposing structured, machine-readable time series. For economists studying retail price dynamics, inflation pass-through, or the construction of online price indices, this limitation represents a significant barrier. We present GIGO, an end-to-end pipeline that combines automated web scraping with calibrated computer vision to reverse-engineer the underlying data from these chart images. The core insight is that metadata already published on the tracking page—specifically, the all-time highest and lowest recorded prices—provides exact anchor points for automatic axis calibration, entirely bypassing the need for error-prone optical character recognition of axis labels. A browser-automation scraper first navigates Cloudflare-protected product pages to collect metadata and high-resolution chart images from Amazon via CamelCamelCamel; a computer-vision module then detects colour-coded calibration references via the probabilistic Hough transform, establishes pixel-to-value mappings for both axes, and traces the price curve through column-wise colour scanning. Applied to a panel of eight consumer-electronics products listed on Amazon, the system recovers over 17 000 daily price observations across 24 price charts (three seller types per product) with sub-pixel temporal resolution and calibration-bounded price accuracy, offering a scalable alternative to both manual chart digitisation and costly API subscriptions.

1 Introduction

Monitoring the evolution of retail prices is a long-standing concern for both consumers and economic institutions. Central banks rely on detailed price data for inflation measurement and monetary-policy design; national statistical offices construct consumer price indices (CPIs) from periodically sampled retail quotations; and competition authorities track pricing patterns to detect collusive behaviour. In recent years, the rapid growth of e-commerce has shifted a substantial share of retail transactions online, prompting a parallel effort to integrate web-sourced prices into official statistics. The Billion Prices Project, initiated by Cavallo and Rigobon (2016), demonstrated that online prices—scraped daily from hundreds of retailers—can closely approximate official CPI movements, often with higher frequency and broader coverage.

A complementary source of online price information is offered by *price-tracking services*. Platforms such as CamelCamelCamel, Keepa, and Idealo continuously monitor product listings on Amazon and other marketplaces, storing multi-year price histories. For individual consumers, these services are invaluable decision-support tools; for researchers, they represent a potential goldmine of longitudinal

micro-price data. The difficulty, however, is one of access. CamelCamelCamel, the most widely used tracker for Amazon, displays historical prices exclusively as rasterised chart images embedded in HTML pages. No public API is provided, and the underlying data cannot be downloaded in any structured format. Keepa does offer a paid API, but access is metered and the cost scales linearly with the number of products monitored, making large-scale studies prohibitively expensive.

This asymmetry—where the data *exists* visually but remains computationally inaccessible—creates a practical bottleneck. Manually digitising a chart is tedious and does not scale beyond a handful of products. Semi-automatic tools such as WebPlotDigitizer (Rohatgi, 2022) require interactive point-and-click calibration for each image. Deep-learning chart-understanding models such as ChartOCR (Luo et al., 2021) and DePlot (Liu et al., 2023) are designed for heterogeneous chart types and lack the domain-specific priors needed for pixel-precise extraction from densely sampled line charts. Even state-of-the-art vision–language models (VLMs) such as GPT-4V (OpenAI, 2023) and Gemini (Google DeepMind, 2024), despite their impressive visual reasoning abilities, struggle with the specific task of recovering thousands of precise numerical observations from a single chart—a point we elaborate on in Section 2.2.

We observe, however, that price-tracking pages expose a valuable side-channel. Alongside each chart, CamelCamelCamel reports exact numerical values for the highest and lowest prices ever recorded, together with the date at which tracking began. These values act as *anchor points* that pin the chart’s axes to known physical quantities, enabling fully automatic calibration without OCR.

Building on this observation, we present GIGO (*Garbage In, Graphs Out*).¹ The system is an open-source, two-stage pipeline: a Python-based scraper first navigates Cloudflare-protected pages and collects product metadata and high-resolution chart images; a computer-vision module then calibrates each chart image against the scraped anchor points and extracts the price curve column by column. The result is a JSON file of daily (`date`, `price`) observations for every tracked product, produced with no manual intervention.

The contributions of this work are threefold. First, we describe an end-to-end, open-source pipeline that bridges the gap between visual price charts and structured time-series data, combining web scraping with classical computer vision in a single automated workflow. Second, we introduce an anchor-point calibration strategy that leverages already-published metadata to bypass OCR entirely, yielding robust and repeatable axis mappings whose accuracy is bounded by the pixel resolution of the chart. Third, we evaluate the pipeline on real-world Amazon price charts for eight consumer-electronics products across three seller types (24 charts total), demonstrating recovery of over 17 000 daily observations with sub-dollar price noise, and discussing the conditions under which the approach succeeds or degrades.

2 Related Work

2.1 Classical and Deep-Learning Chart Extraction

The problem of recovering numerical data from chart images has a long history. Early approaches relied on manual or semi-automatic digitisation: the user identifies axis endpoints, clicks on data points, and the software interpolates coordinates. WebPlotDigitizer (Rohatgi, 2022) remains the most popular tool in this category; it supports a variety of chart types but requires per-image human intervention for axis calibration and point selection, which limits throughput to a handful of charts per hour.

¹A playful inversion of the familiar “Garbage In, Garbage Out” aphorism: the “garbage” is a lossy chart image, and the “output” is a structured graph of price data.

The emergence of convolutional neural networks spurred a new generation of automated methods. Luo et al. (2021) introduced ChartOCR, which decomposes the problem into chart-type classification, axis detection via keypoint regression, and data-mark localisation. Cheng et al. (2023) proposed ChartReader, a transformer-based architecture that jointly parses chart structure and extracts data without hand-crafted heuristics. Masry et al. (2023) presented UniChart, a pretrained vision-language model fine-tuned on a large corpus of chart-table pairs, achieving state-of-the-art results on the ChartQA benchmark. Liu et al. (2023) introduced DePlot, which translates a chart image into a linearised table via one-shot visual reasoning.

These methods are designed for chart-type diversity—bar charts, scatter plots, pie charts, and line charts alike—and are evaluated primarily on question-answering benchmarks (“What is the value of X in year Y?”) rather than on the exhaustive extraction of dense time series. A line chart spanning three years of daily prices may contain several thousand data points; extracting all of them with sub-dollar precision is a fundamentally different task from answering a handful of questions about chart content. Our approach takes the opposite stance: by restricting attention to a single, well-characterised chart format and exploiting platform-specific metadata, we obtain pixel-level calibration accuracy that general-purpose models are not designed to provide.

2.2 Vision-Language Models for Chart Reading

The rapid progress of large multimodal models has made it tempting to treat chart data extraction as a prompting task. Models such as GPT-4V (OpenAI, 2023), Gemini 1.5 (Google DeepMind, 2024), and open-source alternatives like LLaVA (Liu et al., 2024) can interpret chart images and answer natural-language questions about them with surprising fluency. In preliminary experiments, we prompted GPT-4V and Gemini 1.5 Pro with CamelCamelCamel chart images and asked them to extract the complete price history as a structured list.

The results were instructive but ultimately inadequate for our purposes. The models could correctly identify qualitative patterns (e.g., “the price dropped sharply in early 2023”) and approximate landmark values (e.g., “the lowest price was around \$290”), but they failed systematically at dense extraction. Three fundamental limitations emerged. First, *output-length constraints*: even with extended context windows, generating 3000+ structured (`date`, `price`) pairs in a single response exceeds the practical output budget of current VLMs, and chunking the request introduces alignment errors at chunk boundaries. Second, *numerical precision*: the models round prices to the nearest \$5–10 and dates to the nearest month, far below the sub-dollar, sub-day resolution achievable by pixel-level scanning. Third, *hallucination*: in visually dense regions where multiple price lines overlap, the models occasionally fabricated data points or duplicated segments of the series. Moreover, VLM inference is stochastic—repeated queries on the same image yield different outputs—whereas our deterministic pipeline produces identical results on every run. Finally, the per-image cost of commercial VLM APIs (\$0.01–0.05 at the high-resolution tier) would make batch processing of hundreds of chart images significantly more expensive than a local, CPU-only OpenCV pipeline.

These observations reinforce our design choice: for the specific task of exhaustive, high-precision extraction from a known chart format, classical computer vision with metadata-driven calibration outperforms both specialised deep-learning models and general-purpose VLMs.

2.3 Online Prices and Economic Statistics

The use of web-scraped prices in economic research was pioneered by the Billion Prices Project (Cavallo and Rigobon, 2016), which demonstrated that daily online price indices can track official

CPI releases with remarkable fidelity. Cavallo (2017) subsequently showed that online and offline prices are broadly similar for large multi-channel retailers, strengthening the case for web-sourced data in inflation measurement. Aparicio and Misra (2021) provided a comprehensive overview of commercial price-monitoring services, noting that structured data availability varies widely and that many services restrict programmatic access.

Statistical offices have begun to explore scanner data and web scraping as complements to traditional price collection (Eurostat, 2017). The appeal is clear: web data can offer daily frequency, broad product coverage, and near-zero marginal collection cost. However, obtaining clean, structured time series from platforms that do not expose APIs remains a practical challenge. Our work addresses this gap for the specific case of price-tracking chart images, a data source that has so far been overlooked in the literature.

3 Data Collection

The extraction methodology described in the following sections requires two inputs per product: a chart image and a small set of metadata (price extremes, tracking start date). While these could in principle be collected manually, the value of the pipeline lies in its ability to process many products automatically. We therefore include a scraping stage, implemented in Python, that handles product discovery and metadata/image acquisition from Amazon via CamelCamelCamel. We describe it briefly here; the methodological core of the paper is the extraction stage that follows.

Browser automation. CamelCamelCamel deploys Cloudflare’s bot-detection service, which issues JavaScript challenges to incoming requests and blocks those that fail to execute them. Standard HTTP clients such as `requests` or `httr` cannot pass these challenges, making headless-browser automation a necessity. We use `nodriver`, a Python library that controls Chrome through the DevTools Protocol while presenting a browser fingerprint indistinguishable from a regular user session. For each Amazon Standard Identification Number (ASIN) in the input list, the scraper navigates to the corresponding CamelCamelCamel product page, waits for the Cloudflare challenge to resolve, and then extracts the fully rendered HTML.

Metadata extraction. From the rendered page, the scraper parses three elements: a product details table (name, category, tracking start date), a price summary table (all-time lowest and highest prices for each seller type: Amazon, 3rd-party new, 3rd-party used), and the base URL of the chart image server. CamelCamelCamel renders price history as static PNG images served from a dedicated subdomain (`charts.camelcamelcamel.com`), with the chart type, dimensions, and rendering options encoded as URL query parameters. This discovery—made by inspecting the page source for `` tags—enables us to download each chart type (Amazon, new, used) as a separate high-resolution image, avoiding the overlap of multiple price lines that would occur in the combined chart.

Chart image acquisition. Each chart is requested at 2400×1200 pixels (the server accepts arbitrary dimensions via the `w` and `h` parameters), yielding a resolution two to four times higher than the default rendering. The images are downloaded via standard HTTP with a realistic `User-Agent` header and the product page as `Referer`; no browser automation is needed for this step, as the chart server does not enforce Cloudflare challenges.

Algorithm 1 Chart-to-time-series extraction

Require: Chart image I , price extremes $(v_{\text{high}}, v_{\text{low}})$, tracking dates (t_0, t_{end}) , data-line colour \mathbf{c}_d

Ensure: Time series $S = \{(t_i, p_i)\}$

```
1:  $\mathcal{R} \leftarrow \text{CropPlotRegion}(I)$ 
2:  $\hat{y}_{\text{high}} \leftarrow \text{FindCalibLine}(I, \mathbf{c}_{\text{red}}, \text{top } 30\%)$ 
3:  $\hat{y}_{\text{low}} \leftarrow \text{FindCalibLine}(I, \mathbf{c}_{\text{green}}, \text{bottom } 35\%)$ 
4:  $x_{\text{min}}, x_{\text{max}} \leftarrow \text{FindDataExtents}(I, \mathbf{c}_d, \mathcal{R})$ 
5:  $S \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
6: for  $x = x_{\text{min}}$  to  $x_{\text{max}}$  do
7:    $M \leftarrow \text{ColourMask}(I[:, x], \mathbf{c}_d, \delta)$ 
8:   if  $\exists y : M(y) = 1$  then
9:      $y^* \leftarrow \min\{y : M(y) = 1\}$ 
10:     $p \leftarrow v_{\text{high}} - (y^* - \hat{y}_{\text{high}}) / (\hat{y}_{\text{low}} - \hat{y}_{\text{high}}) \cdot (v_{\text{high}} - v_{\text{low}})$ 
11:     $t \leftarrow t_0 + (x - x_{\text{min}}) / (x_{\text{max}} - x_{\text{min}}) \cdot (t_{\text{end}} - t_0)$ 
12:     $S \leftarrow S \cup \{(t, p)\}$ 
13:   end if
14: end for
15: return  $\text{DeduplicateByDate}(S)$ 
```

Anti-scraping countermeasures. Beyond Cloudflare, CamelCamelCamel enforces aggressive rate limiting, returning HTTP 429 responses when requests arrive too quickly, and occasionally presents CAPTCHA challenges after sustained automated access. Our scraper mitigates these defences by introducing randomised delays of 8–15 seconds between consecutive page visits and backing off exponentially upon receiving a 429 or 503 response. These measures proved sufficient for collecting panels of several dozen products, although larger-scale campaigns may require rotating IP addresses or using residential proxies—a strategy we did not pursue for ethical reasons.

All collected data—metadata, price extremes, and image file paths—is serialised to a JSON file keyed by ASIN and passed to the extraction stage.

4 Chart Data Extraction

The extraction stage takes each chart image together with its associated metadata and produces a structured time series of **(date, price)** pairs. The process involves four steps: plot-region detection, calibration-line detection via colour masking and the Hough transform, anchor-point axis calibration, and column-wise data extraction. The overall logic is summarised in Algorithm 1.

4.1 Plot Region Detection

CamelCamelCamel charts follow a highly consistent layout. The plot area occupies approximately 92% of the image width and 94% of its height, with thin margins reserved for axis labels and the legend. We exploit this regularity by defining the plot region as a fixed-ratio crop:

$$\mathcal{R} = [0.04 H, 0.98 H] \times [0.03 W, 0.99 W], \quad (1)$$

where H and W denote the image dimensions in pixels. This deterministic approach avoids the fragility of edge- or template-based plot detection and has proven reliable across all charts encountered in our experiments.

4.2 Colour-Based Masking

All subsequent processing relies on isolating specific chart elements by colour. CamelCamelCamel uses a fixed colour palette: the all-time high price is marked by a **red** dashed horizontal line, the all-time low by a **green** dashed line, and the data curves are drawn in distinct colours for each seller type (green for Amazon-direct, dark blue for 3rd-party new, orange-red for 3rd-party used).

For a target colour $\mathbf{c} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ (in BGR space), we produce a binary mask by thresholding the L^∞ distance between each pixel and the target:

$$M(x, y) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \|I(x, y) - \mathbf{c}\|_\infty \leq \delta, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where δ is a tolerance parameter (typically 35–40 in 8-bit intensity units). The L^∞ norm is preferred over Euclidean distance because it allows independent tolerance on each colour channel, which better accommodates the slight colour shifts introduced by JPEG compression and anti-aliasing.

To suppress false positives, each mask is further restricted to a spatial region of interest. For the red (high-price) calibration line, only the top 30% of the image is searched; for the green (low-price) line, only the bottom 35%. These spatial priors reflect the layout of CamelCamelCamel charts, where the highest price always appears near the top and the lowest near the bottom. Figure 1 illustrates the masking process: panel (b) shows the calibration masks overlaid on the dimmed chart, with white dashed lines marking the spatial search boundaries; panel (c) shows the data-line mask for the 3rd-party new seller; and panel (d) zooms into a high-frequency region where the mask faithfully traces even rapid oscillations.

4.3 Calibration Line Detection via the Hough Transform

Once the colour mask for a calibration line has been computed, the task reduces to locating the dominant horizontal line segment in a binary image. We accomplish this with the probabilistic Hough transform (Matas et al., 2000), a variant of the classical Hough transform that is both faster and more directly suited to our needs.

The classical Hough transform represents each line in the image by a point (ρ, θ) in parameter space, where ρ is the perpendicular distance from the origin to the line and θ is the angle of that perpendicular with respect to the horizontal axis. Every foreground pixel (x, y) in the binary mask votes for all (ρ, θ) pairs consistent with a line passing through it:

$$\rho = x \cos \theta + y \sin \theta. \quad (3)$$

Peaks in the resulting accumulator array correspond to lines that receive many votes, i.e., lines along which many foreground pixels are aligned.

In the classical formulation, *every* foreground pixel casts a vote across the full range of θ , resulting in $O(n \cdot |\Theta|)$ operations for n pixels and a discretised set Θ of angle bins. The probabilistic variant introduced by Matas et al. (2000) avoids this cost by sampling foreground pixels at random and growing line segments greedily: a sampled pixel votes in the accumulator; when a (ρ, θ) cell exceeds a threshold, the algorithm traces the line through the contributing pixels, records the segment endpoints, and removes those pixels from the mask to prevent double counting. The output is a set of line segments with explicit start and end coordinates, rather than an infinite-extent (ρ, θ) parameterisation.

For our calibration task, we configure the Hough transform with parameters chosen to favour the detection of long, thin, horizontal segments. The minimum line length is set to 10% of the

Figure 1: Colour-based masking illustrated on a CamelCamelCamel chart. (a) Original chart with extraction overlay. (b) Calibration masks: the red (high-price) and green (low-price) horizontal lines are isolated by colour thresholding within restricted vertical bands (white dashed lines at 30% and 65% of image height). (c) Data-line mask for the 3rd-party new seller, showing the full price curve isolated from the background. (d) Zoom on a high-frequency region, where the mask captures individual price oscillations.

image width (ensuring that only lines spanning a significant portion of the chart are retained), the maximum gap between collinear segments is set to 3% of the image width (allowing the calibration line to be interrupted by the data curve without being split into disjoint fragments), and the accumulator threshold is set to 5% of the image width. Only segments whose angular deviation from the horizontal is less than 2.5° are accepted.

Because a single calibration line may be detected as several collinear but slightly offset segments (due to the dashed rendering of the line or interruptions by other chart elements), the final step clusters the detected y -coordinates by proximity. All y -values within 7 pixels of one another are assigned to the same cluster. The cluster containing the most segments is selected as the consensus, and its median y -coordinate is taken as the final calibration pixel \hat{y} . This clustering step makes the detection robust to outlier segments caused by stray pixels of similar colour elsewhere in the chart.

4.4 Anchor-Point Axis Calibration

With the calibration pixels in hand, the axis mappings follow by linear interpolation.

For the y -axis (price), let \hat{y}_{high} and \hat{y}_{low} denote the pixel rows of the red and green calibration lines, and let v_{high} and v_{low} be the corresponding price values from the scraped metadata. Because

image coordinates increase downward while prices increase upward, the mapping is:

$$\text{price}(y) = v_{\text{high}} - \frac{y - \hat{y}_{\text{high}}}{\hat{y}_{\text{low}} - \hat{y}_{\text{high}}} \cdot (v_{\text{high}} - v_{\text{low}}). \quad (4)$$

For the x -axis (*date*), we first determine the horizontal extent of the data line by scanning the plot region for the data-line colour and recording the leftmost (x_{min}) and rightmost (x_{max}) columns where it appears. Given the tracking start date t_0 and the scraping date t_{end} (both known from the metadata), the mapping is:

$$\text{date}(x) = t_0 + \frac{x - x_{\text{min}}}{x_{\text{max}} - x_{\text{min}}} \cdot (t_{\text{end}} - t_0). \quad (5)$$

Both calibrations assume a linear relationship between pixels and physical units, which is valid for CamelCamelCamel charts (they use linear, not logarithmic, scales). The anchor-point strategy is the methodological core of our approach: by grounding the mapping in *exact* numerical values published on the page, rather than in OCR-derived approximations that are susceptible to font-rendering artefacts and locale-dependent formatting (e.g., the European convention of commas as decimal separators), we eliminate a major source of error that plagues generic chart-digitisation systems.

4.5 Column-Wise Data Extraction

With both axes calibrated, the price curve is extracted by scanning each pixel column in the range $[x_{\text{min}}, x_{\text{max}}]$. For each column x , a colour mask is generated for the data-line colour (after morphological closing with a 3×3 kernel to bridge small gaps caused by anti-aliasing). Before scanning, the mask is restricted to the *calibration band*—the vertical interval between $\hat{y}_{\text{high}} - \epsilon$ and $\hat{y}_{\text{low}} + \epsilon$ (with $\epsilon = 10$ px)—thereby excluding false-positive pixels from chart titles, legend boxes, and anti-aliased calibration-line edges that happen to match the data-line colour. Within this band, the topmost active pixel $y^*(x) = \min\{y : M(x, y) = 1\}$ is identified. Taking the topmost rather than the centroid is deliberate: because pixel y -coordinates increase downward, the minimum y corresponds to the highest price at that horizontal position, which in turn corresponds to the upper edge of the data line—a consistent and reproducible choice even when the line is several pixels thick.²

The pair $(x, y^*(x))$ is then mapped to $(\text{date}(x), \text{price}(y^*(x)))$ using Equations (5) and (4). Because the pixel resolution typically exceeds one column per calendar day (a chart spanning 1 000 days over 3 000 pixels yields roughly three pixels per day), the raw output contains multiple observations per date. A final de-duplication pass retains one observation per calendar day.

5 Experimental Evaluation

5.1 Setup

We applied the GIGO pipeline to a panel of eight consumer-electronics products listed on Amazon (US). The `nodriver`-based scraper collected metadata and chart images for three seller types per product—Amazon-direct, 3rd-party new, and 3rd-party used—yielding 24 charts in total (two products lacked an Amazon-direct listing, giving 22 Amazon/new/used triples plus 2 new/used pairs). Chart images were downloaded at 2400×1200 pixels, four times the default resolution. The Python extraction module was built on OpenCV 4 and NumPy. All experiments were conducted on a standard laptop

²When the data line is 2–3 pixels wide, the centroid would average the upper and lower edges, introducing a systematic bias of ≈ 1 px. Taking the upper edge avoids this at the cost of a consistent offset of half the line width, which is absorbed by the calibration.

Figure 2: Extraction result for Apple AirPods Pro (2nd gen., Lightning), Amazon seller, tracked from September 2022 to March 2026. Green: original CamelCamelCamel chart. Orange: extracted time series (1 235 points). Dashed lines: calibration anchors (red = \$ 279.99 high; green = \$ 189.00 low; cyan/magenta = temporal extent).

(Apple M-series, 16 GB RAM); the full extraction of all 24 charts completed in under 10 seconds, making batch processing straightforward.

5.2 Detailed Example: AirPods Pro (2nd Generation)

Figure 2 shows the extraction result for the Apple AirPods Pro (2nd generation, Lightning case), sold directly by Amazon, tracked by CamelCamelCamel from September 2022 to March 2026. The green line is the original chart as rendered by the platform; the orange overlay is the time series reconstructed by GIGO (1 235 unique data points). The dashed lines mark the calibration anchors: the red horizontal line corresponds to the all-time high ($v_{\text{high}} = \$279.99$, detected at pixel row $\hat{y} = 95$), and the green horizontal line to the all-time low ($v_{\text{low}} = \$189.00$, detected at $\hat{y} = 989$). The horizontal data extent spans pixel columns 80–2 373, mapping to the full tracking period of 1 272 calendar days.

The price range is narrow (\$ 189–\$ 280, a span of \$ 91), yielding a fine per-pixel price resolution of $\Delta v \approx \$0.10/\text{px}$. The dominant pattern is one of long stable-price plateaux punctuated by sharp, short-lived promotional drops—Black Friday, Prime Day, and seasonal sales—where the price falls by \$ 30–80 for a few days before snapping back. The extraction captures these dynamics cleanly: the sharp edges of the promotional dips are reproduced with 1-day temporal precision, and the flat segments between promotions show near-zero extraction jitter ($\hat{\sigma}_v \approx \$0.18$), consistent with the fine pixel resolution. This product illustrates the pipeline’s strength on Amazon-direct listings, where the price curve is typically a step function with occasional discontinuities—an ideal case for column-wise scanning.

Figure 3: Extraction result for Samsung 49" Odyssey G93SC, Amazon seller, tracked from September 2023 to March 2026. Green: original chart. Orange: extracted time series (904 points). The wide price range (\$898–\$1600) yields a coarser per-pixel resolution of \$0.81/px, yet the extraction faithfully follows both the gradual decline and the sharp promotional drops.

5.3 Second Example: Samsung Odyssey G93SC

Figure 3 shows the extraction result for a product with a markedly different price profile: the Samsung 49" Odyssey G93SC curved gaming monitor, sold directly by Amazon, tracked from September 2023 to March 2026. Compared to the AirPods Pro case, the price range is much wider (\$898–\$1600, a span of \$702), yielding a coarser per-pixel price resolution of $\Delta v \approx \$0.81/\text{px}$ —roughly eight times coarser than the AirPods.

The price trajectory of this high-end monitor is qualitatively richer than that of the AirPods: rather than discrete promotional steps, it exhibits a gradual decline punctuated by sharp drops during sales events and occasional upward corrections. The extraction reproduces both the slow trend and the rapid discontinuities with high fidelity. The coarser price resolution means that extraction noise is larger in absolute terms ($\hat{\sigma}_v \approx \$1.22$), but this remains small relative to the typical price movements of \$50–200 observed in the series. This example demonstrates that the pipeline scales well to products with wide price ranges, where the dominant source of extraction error shifts from pixel quantisation to line-thickness ambiguity.

5.4 Cross-Product Analysis

To assess the pipeline’s robustness across products with different price ranges, tracking durations, and volatility profiles, Table 1 reports extraction statistics for each product using its Amazon-direct chart (or the 3rd-party new chart when the Amazon-direct listing is unavailable). The panel includes a gaming monitor, headphones, earbuds, smartphones, and a smartwatch, with tracking histories ranging from roughly 16 months to over three years and price ranges from under \$100 to over \$1600. In total, the pipeline successfully extracted all 24 charts (three seller types per product), recovering

Table 1: Extraction statistics across the product panel (one representative seller type per product). Δv : per-pixel price resolution. Δt : per-pixel temporal resolution. Coverage: fraction of calendar days with at least one extracted observation. $\hat{\sigma}_v$: estimated price noise (standard deviation of first differences in stable-price periods).

Product	Seller type	Span (days)	Points	Δv (\$/px)	Δt (d/px)	Cov. (%)	$\hat{\sigma}_v$ (\$)
Samsung Odyssey G93SC	Amazon	911	904	0.81	0.40	99.2	1.22
Sony WH-1000XM5	3P New	1 078	949	0.81	0.47	88.1	1.06
AirPods (3rd gen.)	Amazon	671	666	0.10	0.29	99.3	0.16
AirPods 4 ANC	Amazon	541	538	0.10	0.24	99.4	0.14
AirPods Pro (2nd gen.)	Amazon	1 272	1 235	0.10	0.56	97.0	0.18
Galaxy S24+ 512 GB	Amazon	775	755	0.61	0.34	97.4	0.91
iPhone 16 128 GB (Ren.)	Amazon	471	471	0.82	0.21	100.0	1.24
Apple Watch Series 9	Amazon	903	880	0.13	0.39	97.5	0.19

17 391 unique daily observations.

The per-pixel price resolution Δv varies from as low as \$0.10/px for the three AirPods models (whose narrow price ranges of \$76–\$91 are spread over ~ 800 – 900 vertical pixels) to \$0.82/px for the iPhone 16 Renewed (spanning \$549–\$1 278). This variation is expected: the chart’s vertical pixel budget is fixed at ~ 900 pixels regardless of the price range, so products with larger price swings are mapped more coarsely. Temporal resolution Δt depends analogously on the tracking span: the iPhone 16, tracked for only 471 days, achieves the finest temporal resolution (0.21 d/px), while the AirPods Pro, with its 1 272-day history, is compressed to 0.56 d/px.

Coverage—defined as the fraction of calendar days for which at least one observation is recovered—exceeds 97% for all Amazon-direct listings and reaches 100% for the iPhone 16. The Sony WH-1000XM5, which uses the 3rd-party new chart, shows the lowest coverage at 88.1%; this reflects periods where the product was temporarily unavailable from third-party sellers rather than an extraction failure.

The estimated price noise $\hat{\sigma}_v$, computed as the standard deviation of first differences during stable-price plateaux (where the true price is constant and all variation is attributable to extraction error), ranges from \$0.14 (AirPods 4) to \$1.24 (iPhone 16 Renewed). As expected, noise scales with Δv : products with coarser price resolution exhibit larger extraction jitter. Even in the worst case, $\hat{\sigma}_v \approx \$1.24$ is small relative to the typical price movements of \$50–200 observed in high-value products, and negligible for economic analyses of retail price dynamics.

5.5 Resolution Bounds

The precision of the extracted values is fundamentally limited by the pixel resolution of the chart. For the AirPods Pro example, the price range $v_{\text{high}} - v_{\text{low}} = \90.99 is distributed over $\hat{y}_{\text{low}} - \hat{y}_{\text{high}} = 894$ pixels, yielding:

$$\Delta v = \frac{v_{\text{high}} - v_{\text{low}}}{\hat{y}_{\text{low}} - \hat{y}_{\text{high}}} \approx \$0.10 / \text{px}. \quad (6)$$

Similarly, the temporal span of 1 272 days is spread over $x_{\text{max}} - x_{\text{min}} = 2 293$ pixels, giving approximately 0.55 days/px. At the other extreme, the iPhone 16 Renewed chart spans \$728.75 over 894 pixels, yielding $\Delta v \approx \$0.82/\text{px}$. These figures represent theoretical best-case accuracy;

additional error arises from line thickness (typically 2–3 pixels), anti-aliasing at line edges, and colour-thresholding ambiguity. A conservative estimate of the total price error budget is $\pm 2 \cdot \Delta v$, which for the worst-case product in our panel amounts to $\pm \$1.64$ —adequate for virtually any economic analysis of retail price dynamics.

5.6 Pixel-Level Accuracy

In the absence of ground-truth price series (CamelCamelCamel provides no API), we exploit the fact that the chart image *itself* constitutes a pixel-level ground truth. For each chart, the colour mask M of the data line defines which pixels belong to the price curve. After extraction, we render the recovered series back onto the image coordinate system as a one-pixel-wide line padded to the median detected line width \tilde{w} —yielding a *predicted* mask \hat{M} that approximates the original rendering thickness. Standard binary classification metrics are then computed at the pixel level over the data range:

$$\text{IoU} = \frac{|M \cap \hat{M}|}{|M \cup \hat{M}|}, \quad \text{Precision} = \frac{|M \cap \hat{M}|}{|\hat{M}|}, \quad \text{Recall} = \frac{|M \cap \hat{M}|}{|M|}. \quad (7)$$

Table 2 reports these metrics for all 24 charts. Precision is consistently around 0.5–0.6, indicating that roughly half the pixels in the predicted mask fall within the ground-truth mask. Recall varies much more widely (0.04–0.45), and the variation is driven almost entirely by the prevalence of *oscillation zones*—regions where the data line appears unusually thick because the price underwent rapid up-and-down movements within a few pixels of horizontal extent. Charts with low oscillation fractions (e.g., AirPods 4 New, 2.6%) achieve the highest recall (≈ 0.45), while charts with extensive oscillations (e.g., AirPods 3rd gen. Used, 38.4%) show low recall (≈ 0.09).

5.7 Oscillation Detection via Line-Width Analysis

The recall asymmetry in Table 2 reveals a systematic phenomenon that merits separate analysis. When the price undergoes rapid oscillations—rising and falling within a few pixels of horizontal extent—the rendered line becomes a *thick vertical band*: consecutive up-and-down segments fill a strip whose width far exceeds the normal rendering thickness ($\tilde{w} \approx 4\text{--}6$ px). Our topmost-pixel extraction strategy traces the upper envelope of this band, effectively reporting the local maximum price while discarding the valleys.

We detect these oscillation zones by measuring the data-line width $w(x)$ in each column: the number of contiguous mask pixels. A column is flagged as an oscillation zone when $w(x) > 3\tilde{w}$ (or a minimum of 8 px). In these columns, the price difference between the topmost and bottommost mask pixels yields the *oscillation amplitude*:

$$\Delta p_{\text{osc}}(x) = \text{price}(y_{\text{top}}(x)) - \text{price}(y_{\text{bot}}(x)). \quad (8)$$

Across the 24 charts, 17.6% of data columns are flagged as oscillation zones on average, with mean amplitudes ranging from \$15 (AirPods 4 New, a stable product) to \$467 (Samsung Odyssey Amazon, a high-value monitor with large price swings). 3rd-party used charts tend to exhibit the highest oscillation fractions (27–39%), consistent with the volatile pricing typical of marketplace sellers.

This analysis turns a limitation into a feature: the line-width signal acts as a built-in volatility indicator, flagging dates where the single extracted price should be interpreted as an approximate envelope rather than a precise observation. Users of the extracted data can consult the per-column width to assign uncertainty bounds, or extend the extraction to report both the upper and lower prices in oscillation zones, effectively recovering price *bands* rather than point estimates.

Table 2: Pixel-level accuracy and oscillation statistics for all 24 charts. \tilde{w} : median data-line width (pixels). Osc. %: fraction of columns flagged as oscillation ($w > 3\tilde{w}$). $\overline{\Delta p}_{\text{osc}}$: mean price amplitude in oscillation zones.

Product	Type	Prec.	Rec.	IoU	\tilde{w}	Osc. %	$\overline{\Delta p}_{\text{osc}}$
Samsung Odyssey	Amazon	0.562	0.042	0.041	6	27.1	\$ 469
	New	0.592	0.144	0.131	4	17.6	\$ 78
	Used	0.594	0.102	0.095	4	30.4	\$ 70
Sony WH-1000XM5	New	0.594	0.218	0.189	4	14.6	\$ 55
	Used	0.593	0.348	0.281	4	15.4	\$ 19
AirPods (3rd gen.)	Amazon	0.521	0.084	0.078	6	16.6	\$ 52
	New	0.596	0.137	0.126	4	17.4	\$ 21
	Used	0.595	0.088	0.084	4	38.0	\$ 16
AirPods 4 ANC	Amazon	0.565	0.128	0.117	6	13.1	\$ 50
	New	0.599	0.471	0.358	4	1.0	\$ 7
	Used	0.497	0.071	0.066	8	36.4	\$ 25
AirPods Pro (2nd)	Amazon	0.534	0.105	0.096	6	16.5	\$ 39
	New	0.592	0.123	0.113	4	13.5	\$ 31
	Used	0.376	0.208	0.155	40	27.1	\$ 58
Galaxy S24+	Amazon	0.535	0.241	0.199	4	4.2	\$ 119
	New	0.600	0.454	0.348	4	0.7	\$ 119
	Used	0.594	0.138	0.126	4	26.9	\$ 55
iPhone 16 (Ren.)	Amazon	0.544	0.444	0.324	6	3.0	\$ 106
	New	0.409	0.271	0.195	20	18.4	\$ 36
	Used	0.595	0.133	0.122	4	35.6	\$ 22
Apple Watch S9	Amazon	0.530	0.080	0.075	4	7.9	\$ 79
	New	0.594	0.289	0.241	4	5.7	\$ 23
	Used	0.595	0.105	0.098	4	33.8	\$ 30
Mean		0.558	0.187	0.157	7	17.0	\$ 58

6 Discussion

The results presented above suggest that classical computer-vision techniques, when combined with domain-specific metadata, can extract high-fidelity time series from chart images with minimal computational cost. The pipeline is fully deterministic: given the same image and metadata, it produces identical output on every run—a property that commercial VLMs, with their inherently stochastic generation, cannot guarantee. Extraction completes in under one second per chart on a consumer laptop, making it feasible to process panels of hundreds of products in minutes.

From an economic perspective, the ability to recover daily-granularity price series from freely available chart images opens several avenues. Researchers studying price rigidity or the frequency of price changes require exactly this kind of high-frequency micro-data, which has historically been available only through proprietary scanner datasets or expensive API subscriptions. Central banks and statistical offices investigating online–offline price convergence could use GIGO to assemble product-level panels without incurring API costs. The pipeline could also serve as a validation tool: by comparing extracted series against API-sourced ground truth for a subset of products, one could quantify the information loss inherent in chart-based data and assess whether it falls within acceptable bounds for a given application.

Several limitations should nonetheless be acknowledged. The pipeline is tailored to CamelCamel-Camel’s specific visual format—its colour scheme, layout ratios, and calibration-line conventions. Adapting it to another platform (e.g., Keepa, which uses a different chart renderer and colour palette) would require re-specifying the colour constants and possibly the plot-region detection logic,

although the overall architecture and the anchor-point calibration principle would carry over. Our scraper mitigates the seller-type overlap problem by downloading separate per-type chart images from the CamelCamelCamel chart server, but this relies on the availability of that URL endpoint; if it were removed, one would need to fall back to the combined chart and contend with colour-based segmentation errors in regions where anti-aliased edges produce blended pixel colours. Charts with very large price ranges compress the y -axis, degrading per-pixel resolution; conversely, very short tracking histories produce dense temporal sampling but fewer total observations. Any future redesign of CamelCamelCamel’s chart renderer—new colours, new layout, or a switch to canvas-based rendering—would break the hard-coded assumptions and require recalibration.

Several directions for future work could address these issues. The colour constants and layout parameters could be learned from a small labelled training set rather than hard-coded, making the system more robust to gradual visual drift. Sub-pixel interpolation techniques (e.g., fitting a parabola to the cross-column colour intensity profile) could improve effective resolution beyond the one-pixel-per-observation limit. The oscillation-detection mechanism introduced in Section 5.7 could be extended to a full dual-price extraction, recovering both upper and lower envelopes in volatile regions and thereby converting point estimates into price bands. The extracted time series could be systematically validated against Keepa’s paid API for a subset of products, providing a ground-truth benchmark for extraction accuracy. On the economic side, the data could feed into studies of promotional-pricing dynamics, online price dispersion across seller types, or the construction of web-based elementary price indices at the product level.

A note on research ethics: automated scraping may conflict with the terms of service of the data sources involved. Users of GIGO should ensure compliance with applicable policies and consider the implications of large-scale automated access.

7 Conclusion

We have presented GIGO, a two-stage pipeline that recovers structured price time series from the chart images produced by online tracking platforms. By combining a browser-automation scraper capable of navigating Cloudflare-protected pages with a calibrated computer-vision module, the system bridges the gap between visually rendered price histories and machine-readable data. The key methodological contribution is an anchor-point calibration strategy that leverages metadata already published on the tracking page—the all-time price extremes and the tracking start date—to establish exact axis mappings without recourse to OCR or deep learning. Applied to a panel of eight consumer-electronics products listed on Amazon across three seller types (24 charts total), the pipeline recovers over 17 000 daily observations with sub-dollar price noise and near-complete temporal coverage, at a fraction of the cost and complexity of API-based or VLM-based alternatives. We believe this tool can be a useful addition to the methodological toolkit of economists and statisticians who study retail price dynamics in online markets.

Code availability. The complete source code for both pipeline stages is available at <https://github.com/NiccoloSalvini/gigo>.

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